

SPECIFIC FORMS OF LANGUAGE IN PASTORAL COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

The vocabulary is closely related to the basic activity of the communities in the Sibiu area (the so-called "Mărginimea Sibiului"), namely shepherding. In localities based on ancient occupations, an equally ancient language has become established. The communication focuses on specific terms in the field of shepherding, using a vocabulary of everyday activities, traditional household activities and the organisation of elements related to shepherding, and transhumance. Thus, the work presents the names of the trades and objects related to sheep farming, the organisation of the sheepfold, the composition of the sheep flock, the names of products and other activities. Unlike other research, mainly lexicographic, aiming at the hoarding of terms used in shepherding and transhumance, this work illustrates the degree of activity or passivity of these forms of language. The research focuses on the extent to which this vocabulary is still known today, raising the question of its preservation as part of the intangible heritage.

Keywords: shepherding; Mărginimea Sibiului; vocabulary; communication; transhumance; heritage.

INTRODUCTION

The specific language of the communities in the Sibiu region¹ is closely linked to the basic activity carried out here, namely shepherding. In the localities based on ancient occupations, an equally ancient language has become established. This paper identifies aspects of formal and informal communication in pastoral communities and focuses on the terms crystallised in the lexical field of shepherding (with the specific elements of the activity), in the names used in the typology of sheep, in toponyms, in the tools that are today recognised as "ethnographic objects", often in the vocabulary of the gastronomic or traditional domestic area, in folkloric discourse. Thus appear those so-called *cognitive communities*, which Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger discuss by identifying the social relations between newcomers to a locality (as in the case of transhumance) and its indigenous members (2008: 34). It is about shared *learning* (transferable to language) and moving on to shared goals and activities.

The social reality of these communities, through the pastoral language, reflects the work, the crafts, the values, the way of thinking and acting of the inhabitants, combining traditional elements that emerged with the process of transhumance. "We are thus faced with a complex process of acculturation, which gives pastoral language, from a cognitive point of view, a multicultural aspect in which we can read a historical dynamic, a movement of pastoral groups that in the past enjoyed a specific mobility from which monographic sociology, in the variant of researching the phenomenon of urbanization, has remained with the *sheep road*,

¹ The regional terms in this article are based on the works mentioned in the bibliography. Any reproduction of them will be done with respect to copyright.

identifiable even today, from the Mărginimea Sibiului to the Danube Bay" (Olari 2017: 6). The time of wintering also determines this "gone through the country", in search of welcoming plains for the cold season.

The originality of our research is given by the different approaches and with trans-disciplinary references (by calling on linguistic, sociological, folklore, and montanology elements) of the issue of language in pastoral communities because we do not only follow the lexicographical aspects but, above all, the degree of active or passive use of some pastoral terms.

The study we propose focuses on the identification of linguistic elements specific to shepherd areas (and, more specifically, those of the Mărginimea Sibiului, with a focus on Săliște). Words and expressions often have an extremely ancient etymology, highlighting the occupations and continuity of our ancestors on this land. In this regard, researchers note that: "linked to the pastoral landscape, the Romanian language has preserved an important autochthonous, Traco-Dacian linguistic background, specific to animal husbandry (*baci, căciulă, țap, stână, ghioagă, țarc, brânză, gălbează, căpușă* etc.)" (David 2020:99). In this paper we will highlight pastoral terms on predefined structures, as mentioned above (activity/occupations, organization of the sheepfold, sheep names, diseases, sheepfold trades, gastronomy). Subsequently, in order to verify and identify a series of words or expressions that are still preserved in the analysed area, we discussed with several informants of different ages, who highlighted the names maintained and used, as well as the importance in current communication of the related domain. Last but not least, we have used the focus group method as a research technique to identify ways in which pastoral language can be brought to the attention of the general public and preserved over time, using the mass media, i.e. mass communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The shepherds of Mărginimea Sibiului are known as a separate community and are called "ungureni" (Constantin 2014:120). They are in the attention of researchers and recent studies related to the phenomenon of transhumance because the region remains the most important in the country regarding the mentioned phenomenon, which is still practiced here today (Juler, 2014:1). Regarding the various works dedicated to shepherding, there are many studies in this direction. Starting from research related to the entire phenomenon in Europe (Liechti, Biber 2016; Costello, Svensson 2018), which identifies, through a historical vision, the essential features of the activity and reaching also the territory of our country (David 2020, Olari 2017), transhumance was a field of constant interest. Research devoted exclusively to the language of pastoral communities is rare, but there have been concerns about the codification of terms in lexicographical works. We note the appearance of dictionaries made by specialized institutions, such as the case of the recent *Dictionary of Montology* (Covaci et alii 2024), the first bilingual edition edited by a scientific team from the Mountain Economy Center in collaboration with the National Institute of Economic Research within the Romanian Academy. There are also concerns of individual authors who picked up the idiom of their area with terms from various occupations, including shepherding. Thus, regarding the area of Mărginimii Sibiului, we can mention the volumes of Vasile Ursan (2006) focused only on language, as well as a series of works that present shepherding and transhumance, but also include other aspects, apart from the linguistic ones (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015;

Petruțiu 2015). Therefore, established older or newer studies deal with shepherding from an agricultural, economic, zootechnical perspective, etc., even anthropological, cultural, or sociological, but not with an emphasis on the linguistic perspective, as the present article proposes.

SHEPHERDING – ACTIVITY AND ORGANISATION OF THE FLOCK

The lexicon on shepherding shows how this activity requires a real form of organization, nothing is left to chance: *the sheep* (in the local dialect *mânzările*) grazed on the *slopes* (in the romanian dialect: *lăsătorile*) or at the foot of the mountains and hills, and "the shepherdesses who grazed on the mountain tops were left in the care of *the shepherds* (romanian dialect: *sterpari*) and *lambers* (in romanian *mielari*), who sheltered their *flocks* (*tărhatul*) at the "*cotroană*", a kind of sheepfold, made of stone slabs and fir tree. In front of it, between two boulders, was the "*cujba*", the hearth for boiling *mămăliga*. The *vegetables* (*leguma*) and the *corn* (*mălaiul*) were brought by the "*sterpari*" from the *sheepfold* (*sterpari*) on the *slopes* (*lăsători*)" (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 48).

The *baci*, who was the "boss" in the sheepfold, and who was the most authoritative, was helped by a *strungar*, a person who was the most hard-working (*ostenit*) because all the others were also resting (in romanian: *zăcăiau* – they had rest periods). As activities, each one knew exactly his role in sheepfold (and tried to carry it out). From the climbing up the mountain to the taking down of the sheep, the work went on non-stop and organisation was extremely important. For example, it was also important to know the *going of the sheep* on a pasture (*putatul oilor*), because this also knew certain rules, it was not done randomly (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 48). Sheep must be "*turned*" and "*learned*" so that they can graze the grass, not *trample* (*dârâie*) it, and in the evening, after grazing is completed, they are returned to the "*torină*" (the place where they were resting). *The pens* (*țarcuri*) and *sheepfolds* (*oboarele*), the places where the sheep slept, were surrounded by fir-tree *fences* (*lațuri*), fastened with wooden stakes (*gâjuri*), also called pine *logs* (*cepuri*). The flock did not leave until the morning, but *the pen* (*țarcul*) was moved every few days so that the sheep could sleep on a dry place, so that diseases would not "raid" them.

Going out with the sheep was done from a fairly young age, from 14–16 years old, when the boys were considered to be *strong* enough (*în putere*) and able to cope with all the difficult physical chores in the mountains. All the work in the sheepfold was based on the "*haggling*" (*tocmeală*) – the agreement made for a year – which also fixed the payment. In earlier times, the payment/„*simbria*” was not made with money, but mainly with sheep (some sheep from the large flock were given at the end of the work). Nowadays, this custom is no longer maintained, sheep are rarely traded.

As for the family representatives who went to the sheepfold, it is interesting to note that, for example, not in all the villages in the Mărginime were women who went with their husbands to the sheepfold – for example, the women from Săliște stayed at home, taking care of the children and the households in the village, unlike the *Poinărițe* or *Jinaroaie* (women from other villages).

The customs of the work and organisation of the herds were not broken, they were strictly observed, because they were rules that ensured the smooth running of the activity and a transhumance process that became easier to carry out.

Vasile Ursan, addressing the dialect of Mărginimea Sibiului (Ursan 2006: 19–22), mentions the following lexical elements related to the organization of the "stână": *bordeiu*, *strunga*, *țarcu*, *târla*, *sălașul*, *saivanul*, but also others less known: some formed on the Romanian language, many with the agent suffix *-ar*: *cetinar* (pig shelter made of cetine), *fruntar* (a kind of chimney), *spătar* (fence), but also terms borrowed from other languages: *corlată* (narrow part of the lathe, through which sheep pass when milking), *cotroană* (recess in which a fire is made), both borrowed from Hungarian. In addition to these, other examples could be mentioned (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 49–50): *comarnicul* (shingle or pine bark roof), which protected and shielded the *herdsmen* (*mânzărari*) from rain, heat, strong wind, then the *bordeiu*, the actual hut, made of *curved* (*înciocolate*) pine beams (which were joined by interlacing), which had about 2 rooms, with a *cellar* for cheese (*celariul*), but also with sleeping space, where there was *the "păcel"*, a kind of bed covered with *fir cetin/ fallen needle leaves* (*cetină*), *corkboards* (*țolici*), *cobs* (*țoale*) etc.

Among the objects used in shepherding are: *desaga*, *nojița*, *opinca*, *răbojul*, *polița*, *scocul*, *șiștarul*, *cața*, *șerparul*, *sitița*, *țolul*, *barda*, *brișca*, *canta*, *hârdăul*, *lămpaș*, *țundră*, *cazan*, *ceaun*, *cioreci*, *țol*, *tohoarcă*, but also others whose circulation outside the trade is not known, such as those formed on the ground of the Romanian language, of a beautiful expressiveness: *bătac* (large bell), *bătău* (vessel in which butter is beaten), *fânăriță* (manger) *hășcău* (broom with which to stir in the cauldron in which the urda is boiled), *țăcăraie* (small bell), but especially the constructions: *mulgăreață* (bucket in which the sheep are milked) and *urdăreață* (spoon with which the urda is taken out).

Others are taken from Hungarian or German: *budău* (vessel in which butter is kept), *vălău* (trough for watering sheep), *zasc* (polka), *boc* (log) (Ursan 2006: 25–26). The hearth in the shepherd's hut is called *cujbă*, and the *cumna* is the kitchen. If *the canta* is a (larger) mug, the *cănceu* is the wine mug, and the *chindeu* is the towel (Petruțiu 2015: 392). The land on which the sheep slept and which is naturally fattened is called *torină* (Petruțiu 2015: 401).

The expressiveness of the shepherds' vocabulary can also be seen in the variety of suffixes used to make up the names of the objects specific to shepherding. Thus the diminutive suffixes: *-eț/-eață* have an instrumental meaning in the case of the nouns *mulgăreață* and *urdăreață* (formed from the vb. a *mulge*, respectively from the noun *urdă*). The Hungarian suffix *-ău*, which is also used to denote instruments (*bat*, *hare*), is also prolific, while the suffix *-ăraie* (*țăcăraie*), which usually has a collective lexical meaning (e.g. *water-pee*), here indicates a diminutive (*bell*). It is also possible that the name *zârnă* for the bell with the thin sound was formed from the interjection (Petruțiu 2015: 402).

Also related to the organization and activity in the sheepfold, we could mention the dangers or risks to which the shepherds were subjected. Conflicting events or violent, aggressive ones (to which the shepherds responded *with sticks/cu bâta*), were also mentioned by researchers in the field: "by *conflict* in shepherding, we mean a serious disagreement between the personal interests of the shepherds and the authorities, an incompatibility between their opinions and principles and those with whom they are forced to collaborate, to an open, real confrontation with adversaries, either from the same guild, or the authorities, and by *aggression*, violent behaviour and expression, both on the part of natural forces (weather, animals), human attitudes and behaviour, which have an impact on the shepherd and his sheep, and the way in which the shepherd defends himself in response to the aggression to which he is subjected" (Pavelescu 2012:18). From natural calamities (floods,

water, *ghiforul/waterlogging* and frost), to attacks by other animals or *greedy* people (oameni *hrăpăreți*) who wanted to plunder the flock – thieves and robbers, all these sometimes caused the number of sheep to decrease significantly, even to the point of extinction. This gave rise to a saying, mentioned by Nicolae Stan Petruțiu (2010): "The sheep? ... A plow – when they put you in the honor of your head, when they throw you in the ass!" / "Oaia? ... Plug de salcă – când te-așează-n cinstea căsii, când te-aruncă-n fundul mesii!" (Romanian expression).

THE TRADES OF THE SHEEPFOLD

Equally diverse are the names of those who work in the sheepfold. From Vasile Ursan's book the reader learns that in the Mărginimea Sibiului *oierii/ the shepherds* are the owners of the sheep, and *ciobanii/ the herds* are their servants. The terms "*păcurar*" and "*păstor*" are also rarely used. *Mocanul* is the foreign shepherd and *mocănia* is the transhumance. The shepherd's helper is the "*boitar*" or "*povarul*", while the "*simbriaș*" is the shepherd hired for pay (simbrie).

According to the role of the shepherds in the sheepfold, there is *baciul* who milks the sheep, processes the milk, prepares food for the shepherds and keeps the sheepfold clean, the *scutar* who supervises all the activity, and is responsible for the flock in the absence of the *baci*, then the *arendăș* – the one with the most sheep who rents the summer pasture. *Mânătorul* is the shepherd hired to shepherd the sheep in transhumance, *mânzărul* takes care of the milking sheep. The *lamber (mielarul)* is the shepherd of the lambs, *miorarul* looks after the lambs, *sterparul* takes the barren sheep to pasture, the *turner (strungarul)* takes the sheep to the lathe (at the door) to be milked, and *areșarul* is the shepherd of the rams from midsummer until 20 September. *Porneala* is the taking of sheep out to graze after the evening milking.

Interesting are also the names used in relation to the sheep owned: "*târlaşul*" is a man rich in sheep, as opposed to the "*bengulaș*" who is a poor man with few sheep. *Gărarul* is a headless man, an employed shepherd, but *cipcigarul* is a very skilled shepherd. This term comes from *cipcă* (lace) (Ursan 2006:35). In contrast, the lazy shepherd is *zăcăul*. If the shepherds associate they are *ortaci* or *tovarăși*, and for the maintenance of the sheep they have to pay each *aruncul* (plural: *aruncuri* or *aruncări*). In fact, the name of the flock varies according to the number of sheep: the edge of a flock is an *areapă*, a small group of up to 50 sheep is a *clețau/clățau*, up to 100 a *boteu*, between 100 and 300 sheep is a *ciopor* or a *cârd* – between 200 and 400 sheep. The flock (*turma*) consists of more than 500 ewes and the *cart/târla* has more than 800 ewes (Ursan 2006: 33–35). The cart's dowry (*zestrea târlei*) loaded on the donkeys is *tărhatul* (Petruțiu 2015:401).

NAME OF THE SHEEP

Particularly rich is the lexical field of sheep names, which are made according to colour or appearance: thus "*laia*" is the one with dull wool, *oacăra* has rusty spots on its muzzle, the *carabao* sheep (oile *carabașe*) have black spots on its muzzle, the *bighorn* sheep (mioara *revărsată*) has a yellow muzzle, the ram *băl* is completely white, the *buccal* sheep (oaia *bucălaie*) is white with a black muzzle, *burata* or *buzulia* is also white, with black spots but

small on the muzzle, the *ewe lamb* (oaie *oacheșă*) has black spots around the eyes, and *șuta* is a hornless ram (Ursan 2006: 26–29).

In the names used to describe the sheep's appearance, although the colour palette is not very wide – white predominates, combined with black – the variety generated by the size of the colour spots is noticeable, from large spots covering the whole muzzle to small ones.

Other names are related to the use of the sheep: the *mânzare* "has calved and gives milk", the *milking ewe* (oaia *mulgătoare*) is the ewe that is milking, the *barren* (*stearpă*) ewe has not had a lamb in a year, *știră* – the ewe *that is pregnant no longer calves*, *plecătoare* – is the ewe with milk that no longer has a lamb. From Latin the term *arete* is inherited for 'ram' (*berbec*), the *raw* (*crudă*) ewe is the one that has recently calved, the *thick* (*groasă*) or *full* (*plină*) ewe is the pregnant ewe, the *farrowing ewe* (*fătătoarea*) is the ewe ready to calve, *strămioară* is the one that has calved for the first time. It can be seen that the designations here are primarily concerned with adjectival attributes.

The age of the sheep, especially the lambs, is also important. *Strămiorul* is the two-year-old ram, the *junior ram* is *cârlanul/miorul*, i.e. the ram that no longer sucks, *cârlanul* being the lamb from weaning to two years old, while *the tertiary* (*terținul*) or *tertiary* (*terțiu*) is the ram that goes on for three years, as opposed to *vătui* that is up to one year old.

The role of the sheep can be different: *cărmaciul* is the ram that leads the flock, *batalul* is the castrated ram. *Aripoasa* is the sheep at the front of the flock, walking fast as if it had wings. *Babana*, on the other hand, is the old, toothless sheep, and *brăcuita* is beginning to lose its teeth (Ursan 2006: 26–29). The old sheep is also called *botoașă* (Petruțiu 2015: 392).

Sheep are marked in order to recognize them from others, so they can be *buite* (painted with a colour), *cănite* (marked with black) or have different marks applied to them (*cârlig*, *preducea*, *furcuță*, *pișcătură*, *scălușă*, *șuiată*, *tâncușă*, *cioantă*) (Ursan 2006: 30–31). The sheep *de strună* are the good ones for grazing (Petruțiu 2015:398).

Sheep breeds are also diverse: *stogoșă* (a combination of two breeds – țigai+țurcană) (Petruțiu 2015: 400), *țigai* (sheep with fine wool), *țurcană* (long wool with thick wool), *astrahan* (breed of sheep from the region of the same name in Russia), *spancă* (ewe + merino), *caracul* (lambs with curly fur, similar to astrahan), *merinos* (very fine wool).

Related to wool, the *lamb's fleece/ mița* is the first wool to be sheared from lambs, *mițuirea* being the shearing of a lamb. In contrast, *codina* is the lower quality wool from the sheep's head, legs and tail, the shearing of sheep from the belly, tail and legs being called *suvintra* (Ursan 2006: 33). The summer shearing of lambs is a *tușina* (Petruțiu 2015:401).

SHEEP DISEASES

Finally, there are some popular names that refer to the diseases that sheep can contract: *yolk* (hepatitis), *ripening*, *mange*, *soot* (pus), *omag*, *capitis*, *fulminate*, *pluck/thaw*, *cold*, *bloody*, *shed* (*gălbează/gălbenare*) or others named in Romanian dialect as: *coptură*, *râie*, *sugel*, *omag*, *căpială*, *fulgerat*, *însplinare/dalac*, *răceală*, *răsfug*, *sângerat*, *vărsat* (Ursan 2006: 29–30). Of these diseases, some of the most widespread were *yellowness* or *yellowness* (*gălbeaza* or *gălbinare*), considered, at the beginning, to be *without cure*, and *smallpox* (*vărsatul*), which were treated traditionally, with means that shepherds had at hand ("notching a grapevine from the eye" or "passing a needle with silk thread through the ear of the sick sheep").

Shepherds in the Mărginimea Sibiului tried to avoid such *dangers* – "Among the most feared enemies of the sheep flocks, with which the shepherds of Săliște were fighting fiercely, especially through preventive measures, were diseases" (Stănișor apud Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 64–65) – and, in situations where, however, the sheep contacted the various diseases, they fought to cure them (there were a number of traditional methods of combating diseases) or, as a last resort, they proceeded to slaughter the sick sheep or even the entire flock.

GASTRONOMY AND DAIRY PRODUCTS

The terminology in the culinary/ gastronomic area is rich and has been preserved to this day.

It is the production from milk that is the defining production, and the whole process and the resulting preparations have given rise to a diversity of specific linguistic elements. For example, milk was not *creamed* (*smântânit*), curds were made and cheese was stuffed into sheepskin *bellies* (*burduși*). It was the *fat/ rânza* of suckling lamb, which was not taken out to pasture grass, that was used for the *rennet/ cheagul* for the milk. Curd curdling was carried out in large, covered wooden vats (with *sedges/ sedile, curds/ țolici*, etc.). Curd curdling was followed by mixing the *curds* with *străhiata* (*whey*), then the curds were crumbled and placed in a *sedge/sedilă* (cloth sack or cloth itself) tied at the corners, drained and then squeezed. "Stirring was done by placing a wooden log, the *popa*, on top of the curd, over which a lever of boulders was pressed" (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 52–53).

The squeezing action took place while the whey was boiling the udder. The large pieces of curd were left to mature and then placed in the bellows (*burdufi*). The *burdufs/Burdufii* were 10–40 kg and the smaller ones, under 10 kg, were called *teșcoave*. All of them also had a "*țâncuș*", a wood/ (a plank) stuck on them, showing the number of kilos. Around St Mary's Day, the milk was no longer boilable and then *thickened* (*se îngroașă*) into *thick milk* (*lapte acru-sour* milk) stored in pinewood casks. In addition, the much-loved *urdă* was also made, *often eaten raw* (*crudă*) – that is, fresh.

The specific food of the peasants was also based on the products of sheep farming: milk, sheep's milk, curd, curd cheese, *jintița, jeanță, străhiata*, all were not to be missed. In addition, "delicacies" were prepared: *balmoșul* (cornmeal, butter, cream, curd, all cooked in butter), *buzuri* with curd, baked on trays and on a hot hearth (Costăchescu, Ciocan 2015: 56). Also, sheep pastrama or *oloiul*, meat boiled in *its own*, with garlic and lots of onions, were suitable in autumn and winter.

The name of the products is thus more familiar and more often used even today: milk is used to make *curd* (from curdled and squeezed milk), *udder* (from boiling the whey left over from draining the curd), then *telemache* and *curd cheese*. The polenta is also called *coleșă*, and the corner of the bread is called *doțul*. The tool for crumbling the curds at the sheepfold is called the *crestău*, and the wooden vessel through which the curds are squeezed is the *crinta* (Petruțiu 2015:394).

Fresh, unripened curd is called *rennet* (*zămăchișe*), and fresh curd, taken right out of the curdling vessel, is called "*străhăiată*". *Mash* is the thickened, trapped milk. *The whey* or *jinth* can be drunk, the word "*pitch*" (*smaală*) is also used for *cream*, and the *rennet/cheag* extracted from the stomach of the suckling lamb is necessary for curdling the milk. In the Mărginime, the cheese curd is, as previously mentioned, the *buz* (Ursan 2006: 31–32). In

contrast, the verb to *curdle/a zbârcăi* refers to "to milk the last drop of milk" (Petruțiu 2015:402).

METHODOLOGY

In order to observe the extent to which terms specific to sheep farming are present in the current vocabulary, four *informants* from the Mărginimea Sibiului, belonging to different generations, were used. These interviewees now live in both urban and rural areas. An attempt was made to identify current linguistic elements, but also those that could (re)present a revival of the traditional and the shepherd in Romanian society.

The assumptions were as follows:

- The specific forms of the vocabulary of the shepherd are known and used to a large extent in rural language;
- Regional terms are partly known but no longer used in urban language;
- Term preservation is necessary through conservation and educational means.

Thus, for the 54-year-old IC, some of the terms used in the Mărginime are known through family vocabulary, from the informal language of his father, originally from Săliște. Thus she knows the meaning of terms such as *buit, cănit, boc, cantă, cănceu, chindeu*, but does not use these terms. Of the product-related names she knows and uses, the regional ones used are *jintiță* and *buz*. Most of the terms specific to shepherding are known by way of the book, from works of Romanian literature on shepherding. These are popular terms such as: *mioriță laie/bucălaie, ochioasă, saivan, cioareci, toharcă, saivan, târlă, strungă*, etc. Some of these are used occasionally, such as *cioareci, saivan, turmă*. Regional terms used more frequently in the shepherd's trade, such as *străhiată, bățu, mulgăreață, fruntar*, etc., are not known.

Even for the 86-year-old IM, who was born and raised in Săliște, the terms specific to sheep farming are not (anymore) known. In addition to those already mentioned by IC, he also knows *the preducea* as "the tool with which to make holes".

The 62-year-old MC, who has lived in Săliște for over 40 years (and also comes from the Mărginimea Sibiului) admits that she can identify a considerable number of pastoral terms, but they are increasingly rarely used in everyday speech. Among the more familiar linguistic elements are those relating to sheep names – *bucălaia, oacheșă, laie, băl, stearpă, mulgătoare*, as well as a number showing traditional objects or activities in the sheepfold. In addition, terms have been mentioned which are still in common use today. These terms come either from sheep breeds and highlight the materials from which the clothing is made – such as *merinos* – the finest wool or *astrahan* – a term which, by metonymy, today refers to various items of clothing or, in most cases, from gastronomy and dairy or mutton products. Terms such as *balmoș, buz, jintiță, străhiata*, then *oloi and său* (to which sheep's *pastrami* is also added) were mentioned.

But for 41-year-old MM, who comes from a family of sheep farmers, most of the terms are still well known, even if not all of them are used anymore. Among the objects used in the sheepfold, the terms *crestău, crintă, vălău și cănceu* are known. Most of the words in the active vocabulary are related to the naming of sheep, their breeds and diseases, as well as to the marking of sheep using different procedures. Thus, with regard to appearance, the terms "*laie*", "*băl*", "*bucălaie*", "*oacheșă*", "*șută*" are known, as are aspects related to the role of sheep, such as *mulgătoare, mânzare, plecătoare, strămioară* sau *stearpă*. Also known are the names

for the size of the flocks of sheep, as well as the shepherd's trades (*boitar, mǎzǎrar, strungar, oier, mocan, târlaş*). The names of the products are also used. A few terms are recognised but no longer used. For example, the term '*coleşă*' was only used by the grandparents' generation for polenta, the others still know the meaning from the older generation's use.

A second tool used was a focus group. This is a "qualitative research technique (...) that combines the characteristics of focus interviews with those of group interviews" (Chelcea 2022:309). Such features, mentioned by Septimiu Chelcea, are related to the participants (an operator and a group of interviewees), its structure and the time allocated to identify the opinion of the participants. For the present study, a focus group was conducted with second year students – specialising in Journalism (12 people participated), on the ways of preserving terms and educating the public.

RESULTS

All focus group participants agreed that the media has an important role in preserving the Romanian language. Asked what kind of programme could be made for educational purposes, the students suggested different programmes, depending on the media channel. For audiovisual, the students were of the opinion that a reportage-type programme would be suitable, with the presentation of authentic folk creators from the Mărginimea Sibiului presenting and explaining different objects specific to sheep farming. For the audio channel and print media, an interview with a person who is well-known to a general audience, such as Gigi Becali or Ghiță, the Shepherd, was proposed. All the suggested materials contain to a greater or lesser extent elements of entertainment, the TV show proposes a contest and public vote and the interviews approach a humorous style.

The evaluation of the results shows that the first hypotheses are confirmed, with the observation that the vocabulary of sheep farming is less and less used, because the profession of sheep farmer has become very restricted, which is why the terms are less and less used, even in rural areas. The area where more words and expressions are still widespread is gastronomy – a revitalisation can be achieved in this area, especially by appealing to traditional products that are appreciated for their unrivalled taste, quality and biodiversity. However, most of the terms are now used or known only to sheep-farming families, but here too the terms are being lost as generations disappear. It is expected that without a policy of preserving and supporting these words, they will in time disappear altogether not only from the active vocabulary but also from the passive vocabulary of speakers, more quickly in urban areas and more slowly but surely in rural areas.

The third hypothesis is partially confirmed. The focus group discussions show that the media is an important resource that can be used to cultivate this vocabulary, but only in combination with an entertainment or even a performance component to counteract the weak effect of the media. This could involve interactive elements (competitions, public voting) or communication of a show-off and attention-grabbing nature (with the participation of well-known public figures from the entertainment world).

The present study contributes, by researching the terms used in pastoralist communities, to the knowledge of their active use, unlike dictionaries made by authorized institutions or single authors. The linguistic corpus of transhumance is preserved in lexicographical works. Much less is known about the use and knowledge of these terms by speakers today. On the

one hand, our approach could be used as a method to identify the terms used in other sheep communities in different areas of the country. On the other hand, it can be an alarm signal or a reason for various institutions to come up with practical means to preserve this cultural heritage so precious and, at the same time, so fragile.

CONCLUSIONS

The names used in formal and informal communication in the field of sheep farming and transhumance are undoubtedly an important part of the intangible heritage. Mărginimea Sibiului is an important community known for shepherding as a basic occupation.

Today many words from the general lexicon, used throughout the countryside without necessarily being related to the shepherd's trade, are preserved, both thanks to literature and communication still alive in the Mărginime. Thus we find words such as *țol*, *toharcă*, *râie*, *vărsat*, *cață*, *serpar*, *poliță*, *lămpaș*, etc. Others are from the field of sheep farming, preserved through inherited folklore such as the verses from *Miorița* which speak of *miorița laie*, *laie*, *bucălaie*.

Few words have been passed on to the second and third generations, who no longer live in the village, no longer (any longer) engage in shepherding, but have heard specific terms from the vocabulary of their parents and grandparents such as: *a bui*, *cănit*, *cantă*, *boc*, etc. With modernisation and the evolution of society, generations have become separated from the tradition of transhumance and no longer use or understand most of the words specific to this occupation. Who still knows what *crinta*, *sacăteu* or *preduceaua* is? Possibly only those concerned with this field, such as research in the field of mountaineering, who use and know terms related to sheep names (*noaten*, *batal*, *oacheșă*) and other terms related to sheep farming, but it is only a very limited, informed public.

Also, regionalisms specific to the area such as *buz*, *jintiță*, *samăchișă*, *țâncușul*, *popa* and so on are still used by the inhabitants of Mărginimea Sibiului, but for how long? Efforts must be made not only to prevent the traditional trades from being forgotten, but also to prevent the lexicon, which is so expressive and part of our intangible heritage, from being forgotten. A concentrated effort is needed from the various institutions. In addition to media broadcasts, which unfortunately rely on entertainment, often easy, for a better audience, other institutions such as schools, libraries or other organisations could propose not only a weaving or sewing workshop, but also a workshop or a shepherding lesson in which the customs, terms or even routes used in shepherding and transhumance are revived.

The limitations of the present study come from the research of terms from only one region of Transylvania, Mărginimea Sibiului, where transhumance has the most solid tradition. In **future research**, we find the study as a starting point for others who will approach the vocabulary of pastoralism and can relate, complement, or fix the observations with aspects from other regions (synchronic research) or from different periods (diachronic research).

Thus, all these elements related to the linguistic aspects in the sheep areas represent possibilities to learn about the communities there, emphasizing, as previously observed, that: "ethnography, ethnology, and folklore are a scientific source for the sociological study of pastoral life. Ethnographic, ethnological, and folkloristic materials thus represent, for pastoral sociology, the quality of social documents" (Olari 2017: 6).

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